

Role of Yoga on Subjective Wellbeing and in the Management of Lifestyle

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INTRODUCTION

"The state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely absence of disease or infirmity" is how the World Health Organization defines health. One essential technique for achieving that "state" of health is the yogic way of life. It is crucial to remember that feeling and "being" healthy are two different things entirely.

The healthiest lifestyle ever created, yoga's comprehensive art and science is excellent in managing common lifestyle illnesses like diabetes and hypertension. It's interesting that contemporary research has started to concentrate on the positive psycho-physiological effects of yoga, which should be viewed as more than just a type of physical activity.(1,2)

A yogic diet, lifestyle, mindset, and practices all contribute to the development of positive health and self-strength, making people more resilient to stress. By normalizing the experience of stress, optimizing the response to it, and successfully releasing pent-up tension through a variety of yoga practices, this yogic "health insurance" is attained. Yoga is a comprehensive and integrated life science that addresses mental, emotional, spiritual, and physical well-being.

The majority of people assess their circumstances as either positive or negative, and they are typically able to make judgments concerning their life. Humans almost constantly experience moods and emotions, which are characterized by a hedonic component that can be either pleasurable or unpleasant, indicating a positive or negative response. In psychology and medicine, therefore, subjective well-being is becoming a

key diagnostic and outcome variable. Individuals continuously and subjectively evaluate their well-being, even when they don't give it much thought. Subjective well-being (SWB) is the term used to describe how individuals assess their lives. It encompasses factors like moods and emotions, anxiety and sadness, life and marriage satisfaction, and moods. For millennia, the concept of SWB, or happiness, has captivated intellectuals. One strategy to raise the standard of living has been to look for healthier lifestyles and better techniques for managing stress, which enhances subjective well-being. These discoveries have introduced us to age-old practices like yoga, which blend the nutritional components of a well-rounded lifestyle with effective remedies for long-lasting mental tranquility (3). Additionally, the development of psychoneuroimmunology has reinforced the scientific underpinnings of mind-body medicine (4). Since positive mind-influencing techniques are now widely used to treat a wide range of disorders (5).

YOGA'S PART IN MANAGING THE STRESS REACTION

Since stress is a major factor in the onset, exacerbation, or worsening of all lifestyle problems, it is critical to realize that yoga can help us better manage our stress. Streeter et al. postulated a theory based on the idea that yoga practices lower allostatic load in stress response systems, restoring optimal homeostasis, to explain the advantages of yoga in a variety of often coexisting medical problems.

1. An imbalance in the autonomic nervous system (ANS), with more sympathetic and less parasympathetic activity
2. The main inhibitory neurotransmitter system, the gamma aminobutyric acid system, is underactive. (6)

YOGIC MANAGEMENT OF DISORDERS IN LIFESTYLE

1. Psychological retraining and the cultivation of suitable mindsets like pratipaksha bhavanam, chaturbhavana, and yama-niyama
2. Managing stress with jathis, asanas, kriyas, counseling, and pranayama

3. Using physical activities like pranayama, kriyas, asanas, and surya namaskar to help restore normal metabolic function(6,7)

A YOGIC APPROACH TO LIFESTYLE DISORDERS: PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT

CREATION OF RIGHT BEHAVIORS

In order to address lifestyle diseases, cultivating positive attitudes through the development of yogic attitudes toward all aspects of life is crucial. This is essential to lessen stress, which is typically an internal overreaction rather than a reaction to any outside stimuli. The therapist is to inculcate the attitudes advocated by Maharishi Patanjali (maitri, karuna, mudita, and upekshanam) in order to help the patient achieve clarity of mind (chitta prasadhanam). Therapists should emphasize the value of the patient adopting an opposing perspective toward self-defeating ideas and behaviors (pratipaksha bhavanam), in addition to cultivating the principles of Karma, Raja, and Bhakti yoga in daily life.

A HEART-FRIENDLY DIET

It is vital to maintain a healthy diet. Regular mealtimes are important, as are sufficient servings of sprouts, bitter melon, fenugreek, turmeric, and green vegetable salads. Neem is also important. The diet should contain as little salt as possible as well as enough potassium and calcium, which can be found in fruits and low-fat dairy products. Maintaining adequate hydration is crucial, and therapists must emphasize that losing a few kilograms of body weight will improve insulin sensitivity and lower blood pressure. A few helpful guidelines are to eat only when you're hungry and only after your last meal has had time to digest; to eat small, frequent meals rich in complex carbs; and to stay away from processed and junk food.

PRACTICES FOR COORDINATING BREATH AND MOVEMENT

Emphasis should be placed on techniques that improve mind-body harmony by utilizing "breath-linked movements." In this context, Sukshma vyayama and Sheetalikarana

vyayama techniques are helpful, as are the delightful jathis of the Gitananda school. Slowly performed with awareness of breath, surya namaskar can also result in psychosomatic harmony. The postures can also be sustained strain-free for a brief amount of time with meditative awareness of the surya mantras.

ASANAS IN YOGA

The following asanas may be modified to suit the patient's physical condition and any coexisting medical issues. It is beneficial to perform standing poses such padottana, hasthapada, padangushta, mehru, and tada inversions. Bhujanga asana and Ardha Shalabha asana are beneficial standing poses, and vakra, gomukha, ushtra, shashaha, and yoga mudra asana are a few beneficial sitting poses. Matsya asana, pavana mukta asana, and eka and dwipada uttanpada asana are among the supine poses. Poses with a top-turvy shape may aid in resetting the baroreceptor reflex processes that control blood pressure. In the event that the patient is unable to do postures like sarvanga and sethubanda sarvanga asana, similar results may also be obtained with "head-below-heart" poses.

CONCLUSION

Yoga has a lot of potential for treating and preventing diseases and lifestyle issues, and adopting a yogic lifestyle can significantly enhance the general public's health. Yoga may slow the disease's progression and, if practiced early enough, may even result in a cure.

The main health benefits of yoga might be attributed to its lifestyle components as well as the yogic relaxation and pranayama's psychosomatic balancing effects. Yoga, as practised traditionally, refers to both the practice and the completion of achieving a healthy and balanced state.

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